

Experiences of models@run-time with EMF and CDO

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Abstract

Model-driven engineering promotes models and model transformations as the primary assets in software development. The models@run-time approach provides an abstract representation of a system at run-time, whereby changes in the model and the system are constantly reflected on each other. In this paper, we report on more than three years of experience with realising models@run-time in scalable cloud scenarios using a technology stack consisting of the Eclipse Modelling Framework (EMF) and Connected Data Objects (CDO). We establish requirements for the three roles *domain-specific language (DSL) designer*, *developer*, and *operator*, and compare them against the capabilities of EMF/CDO. It turns out that this technology stack is well-suited for DSL designers, but less recommendable for developers and even less suited for operators. For these roles, we experienced a steep learning curve and several lacking features that hinder the implementation of models@run-time in scalable cloud scenarios. Performance experiences show limitations for write heavy scenarios with an increasing amount of total elements. While we do not discourage the use of EMF/CDO for such scenarios, we recommend that its adoption for similar use cases is carefully evaluated until this technology stack has realised our wish list of advanced features.

Keywords model-driven engineering, models@run-time, model repository, eclipse modelling framework, connected data objects

1. Introduction

Model-driven engineering (MDE) aims at improving the productivity, quality, and cost-effectiveness of software development by shifting the paradigm from code-centric to model-centric. In MDE, models and model transformations are the main artefacts of the development process. Often, models are specified using general-purpose languages such as the Unified Modeling Language (UML) [12]. Yet, to fully unfold the potential of MDE, models are specified using domain-specific languages (DSLs) tailored to a specific domain of concern, *e.g.*, the Cloud Application Modelling and Execution Language (CAMEL)¹ [16, 18].

Models@run-time [4] is an architectural pattern for dynamically-adaptive systems that leverages upon models at both design-time and run-time. In particular, models@run-time provides an abstract representation of the underlying running system, whereby a modification to the model is enacted on-demand in the system, and a change in the system is automatically reflected in the model.

The combination of the Eclipse Modelling Framework (EMF)² and Connected Data Objects (CDO)³ facilitates the development of models@run-time and represent the primary focus of this paper. EMF is the de-facto standard in MDE and consists of a framework for (meta)modelling and code generation. EMF provides Ecore, a core metamodel that allows specifying Ecore models. CDO is part of EMF, and

¹<http://camel-dsl.org>

²<https://www.eclipse.org/modeling/emf/>

³<https://www.eclipse.org/cdo/>

Figure 1. Models@run-time with CDO

provides a persistence framework that works natively with Ecore models and their instances.

In this paper, we report on more than three years of experience using EMF and CDO to realise models@run-time in the three cloud research projects PaaSage⁴, CACTOS⁵ [19] and CloudSocket⁶. In particular, we provide a three-fold contribution: (i) We identify three main roles in models@run-time, assign them specific tasks in the life-cycle of models@run-time, and derive requirements for tools in order to support for models@run-time. (ii) For each role, we reflect our experiences of more than three years designing DSLs with, developing for, and operating EMF/CDO in scalable cloud applications. (iii) Based on these experiences, we derive a wish list to the EMF/CDO developers on how to extend the tools.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 introduces a models@run-time scenario in the cloud, derived from three research projects; identifies the related roles; and derives their respective requirements. Section 3 sketches the technology stack consisting of EMF and CDO. Section 4 describes our experiences for each role and the experienced performance. Section 5 discusses our experiences and presents the lessons learnt and a wish list of advanced features. Section 6 discusses related work, before Section 7 concludes the paper and outlines future work.

2. Models@run-time for the Cloud

We acquired our experiences in the PaaSage, CACTOS, and CloudSocket projects, which share the adoption of models@run-time to support the execution of cloud applications.

PaaSage delivers a platform to support modelling and execution of cloud applications on multiple clouds together with an accompanying methodology to allow model-based provisioning, deployment, and adaptation of these applications independently of the existing underlying cloud infrastructures.

⁴<http://www.paasage.eu>

⁵<http://www.cactosp7.eu/>

⁶<https://www.cloudsocket.eu/>

CACTOS provides a toolset for data centre operators, which facilitates dealing with the increasing scale, heterogeneity, and complexity in cloud data centre infrastructures. CACTOS relies on a model-based representation of the physical and virtual infrastructure and derives self-adaptive optimisations based on these models.

-CloudSocket uses concept models and semantics to align domain-specific business processes with executable workflows. These are enabled in a multi-cloud environment addressing business needs by the Business Process as a Service (BPaaS) paradigm.

The projects PaaSage, CACTOS, and CloudSocket have in common: (i) a centralised models@run-time environment to allow the programmatic manipulation of models; (ii) a centralised actuator to enact changes by reasoners; (iii) probes deployed on multiple nodes, virtual machines, and workflow engines to gather the actual application state; and (iv) a technological stack consisting of EMF and CDO.

From these commonalities, we derive a models@run-time scenario in the cloud.

2.1 Models@run-time Scenario in the Cloud

Figure 1 sketches the models@run-time architecture of our scenario in the cloud: A domain-specific reasoner reads the current model in the CDO Server (step 1) and produces a target model (step 2). Then, an actuator computes the difference between the current model and the target model, and enacts the adaptation by modifying only the parts of the application necessary to account for the difference (step 3). Finally, the actual application state is gathered by probes (step 4), and the target model becomes the current model (step 5).

2.2 Models@run-time Roles

While working with models@run-time, we observed that the same responsibilities were assigned to groups of individuals in all three projects. This led to the definition of the following three roles: *DSL designer*, *developer*, and *operator*. While the DSL designer is well known in MDE, the two others so far have barely been considered by other authors, especially in the context of models@run-time. Yet, in practise,

Working area	DSL designer metamodels	Developer models	Operator system
Transaction	-	consistency, concurrency	-
Validation	constraints	stability	-
Versioning	evolution	history	-
Scalability	metamodel size	model size	load capability
Access control	-	-	security
Durability	-	-	data persistence
Notification	-	change propagation	-
Usage interfaces	creation	access models	administration

Table 1. Requirements towards models@run-time per role

they are crucial for realising system integration and system operation.

Please note that the typical role of the *modeller*, who specifies and manipulates models in a general-purpose or domain-specific language, is outside the scope of this paper. This is because we are concerned with the run-time manipulation of models performed by software components such as reasoners, rather than the design-time manipulation of models performed by humans. The interested reader may consult [10] for an empirical study of the state of the practice and acceptance of MDE, which focuses on the modeller.

The **DSL designer** describes the modelling concepts, their properties and their relations, and rules for combining these concepts to specify valid models in a DSL. Usually, this is realised by a metamodel along with attached constraints.

The DSL designer requires a friendly *user interface* (UI) to specify metamodels. Moreover, he requires another UI to specify and attach *constraints* to metamodels, which ensure the *validity of models* at both design- and run-time. Furthermore, he requires that the *number and complexity of the metamodels* is not limited by technical constraints. Finally, the DSL designer requires support for the *versioning* and *co-evolution* of metamodels, which enables an iterative development process.

The **developer**⁷ writes business code that connects third-party systems with the model repository. In particular, the developer provides actuators that transform model changes to actions performed on the underlying system. In order to automatically fill the models, the developer provides probes that gather data from the underlying system and feeds them into the model.

In order to interact with the repository, the developer relies on an *API*. To avoid constant polling for tracking changes, *push notifications* by the repository are desirable. For enabling *concurrent access* to the models, a mechanism to ensure a *consistent* state in the repository is required, ideally enhanced with mechanisms that ensure a *valid model*. Accessing the repository via the *API growing workloads* shall not lead to the starvation of queries.

⁷used as a generalised term also capturing system architects

The **operator** runs the infrastructure including the model repository, the back-end services, the actuators, and the probes. The operator wires all entities, enabling their communication, and enacts security and integrity of the repository by providing adequate access control as well as backup mechanisms.

An operator is dependent on *valid documentation and configuration guidelines* in order to configure the system and realise *stability and performance tuning* of the services. An operator needs ways to *monitor* the actual performance of the repository to analyse and fix performance bottlenecks, e.g., by scaling out. Fine-grained *security access* ensures system integrity. Ideally, the operator is supported by an *administrative user interface*. In order to cope with long-running software services, *durability* of stored data is of utter importance.

2.3 Requirements Towards Models@run-time

In order to be able to evaluate a models@run-time environment, we introduce requirements based on the descriptions of the roles. Table 1 lists those consolidated requirements based on the description of the roles. The table also shows the relation between requirements and roles. *Transaction* describes the capability of applying atomic updates to and consistent reads from the repository as well as concurrent access. *Validation* enables the verification of the validity of the models. *Versioning* supports access to the history of the models, i.e., the changes applied to a model. In addition, it captures the capability to follow changes of the metamodel and evolve the repository content to newer versions of the metamodel. The semantics of *scalability* is three-fold: For the DSL designer, it represents the capability to define metamodels of arbitrary size; for the developer, it describes the capability to use models of arbitrary size; whereas for the operator, it enables the feature to extend the repository with new storage and processing power at run-time to provide sufficient storage size and to serve enough requests [5]. *Access control* offers the capability to specify and enforce access rights to possible different parts of the repository in a sufficiently fine-grained manner. *Durability* describes the ability to store models in a persistent way that

survives crashes and server out-takes. *Notification* supports the installation of callback handlers with the repository that informs about changes in the models. *Usage interfaces* summarise all ways of interacting with the repository ranging from the definition of metamodels over the capability to access and modify existing models to the administration of the repository, *e.g.*, for registering metamodels or changing access rights. Besides the requirements towards models@run-time, the overall performance experience especially in a productively used, large scale set up is of interest.

3. Technology Stack

In this section, we describe the features of the technology stack we adopted in the context of self-adaptive, cloud applications. The stack description is not intended to be exhaustive, but only aims to present the necessary background for the reasoning in the remainder of this paper. We start with an overview on EMF followed by a sketch of CDO and its features.

3.1 Eclipse Modeling Framework (EMF)

In EMF, metamodels are Ecore models that conform to the Ecore metamodel (*cf.* Figure 2). The Ecore metamodel, in turn, is an Ecore model that conforms to itself (*i.e.*, it is reflexive). Ecore models and their instances can be either manipulated manually through UIs or programmatically through Java APIs.

EMF provides frameworks such as Eclipse OCL⁸ to validate models against Object Constraint Language (OCL) [13] constraints attached to the metamodel. It also provides additional frameworks such as the Graphical Modeling Framework (GMF)⁹ and XText¹⁰ to define concrete (graphical or textual) syntaxes and realise IDEs for DSLs.

Finally, EMF comes with three persistence providers: XML Metadata Interchange (XMI) [14] files, EMFStore¹¹ and CDO. This paper only considers CDO as it is the most mature persistence provider [3] for distributed applications.

3.2 Connected Data Objects (CDO)

CDO is a semi-automated persistence framework that works natively with Ecore models and their instances. It abstracts from the specific underlying database and automatically takes care of the bi-directional mapping of models to (relational) data.

The CDO Server represents the model repository comprising the actual server and a database as storage back-end as depicted in Figure 1. It supports several database management systems (DBMS), including relational databases such as MySQL, but also NoSQL databases such as MongoDB.

⁸<http://wiki.eclipse.org/OCL>

⁹<https://www.eclipse.org/modeling/gmp/>

¹⁰<https://eclipse.org/Xtext/>

¹¹<http://www.eclipse.org/emfstore/>

3.2.1 Client-side aspects

The Java API represents models as sets of CDO objects. CDO objects accessed by the client stay logically attached to their pendant in the repository. This mechanism enables CDO to support features beyond EMF such as *lazy loading* and *notifications* upon changes.

CDO revisions allow accessing and reproducing the history of changes of CDO objects. CDO provides the concept of *transactions* and *views* to deal with concurrent access to the repository. A transaction has to be used for write operations, views are supposed to be applied for read-only access.

Based on CDO objects and CDO revisions, CDO supports the concept of *optimistic versioning* [17]. This means that clients first change the state of objects locally, before re-synchronising the changes with the server, *e.g.*, through committing a transaction. In addition to its Java API, CDO offers the query language interfaces Structured Query Language (SQL), Object Constraint Language (OCL), and Hibernate Query Language (HQL) to retrieve and manipulate content.

3.2.2 Server-side aspects

The server implementation is based on OSGi [1]. This modular platform promises an extensible architecture where additional features such as security can be enabled by adding the respective bundles to the server core.

The mapping from CDO logic to DBMS invocations is realised by *database store* bundles. Each store comes with dedicated capabilities and supports a limited number of DBMS. For instance, the DB store can be associated with any DBMS supported by a JDBC driver and the MongoDB store uses the document-oriented MongoDB for persistence.

3.3 CDO Features Towards Models@run-time

Based on the outlined conceptual and technical capabilities, CDO offers a feature set that satisfies the design-time and run-time requirements of the self-adaptive cloud applications as described in Section 2.3. Table 2 shows the models@run-time requirements and the respective CDO feature that claims to fulfil the requirements.

4. Experiences

In this section, we summarise our experiences with EMF and CDO in the context of models@run-time for cloud applications. For each of the roles, we compare CDO's capabilities from Section 3.3 against the role-specific requirements defined in Section 2.3. The section concludes with a performance evaluation in Section 4.4.

4.1 Experiences as a DSL Designer

CDO was developed with MDE in mind and hence, is able to satisfy many of the requirements a DSL designer actually has for defining metamodels: EMF supports a graphical editor allowing an intuitive **creation** of metamodels. Here,

Figure 2. CDO platform architecture in a self-adaptive cloud context

Working area	Relation to CDO feature
Transaction	Transactional manipulations of the models persisted in the repository.
Validation	Automatic checking of the conformance between the models persisted in the repository against their metamodel along with the attached constraints.
Versioning	<i>Optimistic</i> versioning[17] of the models persisted in the repository, where each client of the repository has a local (or working) copy of the models.
Scalability	Arbitrary size of the models persisted in the repository, exploiting mechanisms such as caching and lazy loading.
Access control	Role-based access control to the models persisted in the repository, supporting the controlled access to (parts of) models.
Durability	Multiple store implementations with different databases.
Notification	Automatic notification of clients about changes in the state of the models persisted in the repository.
Usage interfaces	Eclipse-based UI and API for direct and programmatic manipulation of models, respectively.

Table 2. Requirements mapped to CDO features

we did not experience any problems with the **scalability** of metamodels. The integration of OCL in the metamodels proved expressive enough to specify also complex constraints. The constraint checking by EMF is seamless by both EMF and CDO and effectively supports the **validation** of models at both design-time and run-time.

On the down-side, the learning curve of OCL is steep making it hard for newcomers to get familiar with it. Indeed, this is an inherent limitation of OCL rather than EMF or CDO. Besides, the DSL designer is forced to perform synchronisation of OCL constraints manually—a time-consuming and error-prone process. In our experience DSL designers further suffered from the lack of **versioning**. This required to manually migrate models to updated metamodels; again, an error-prone and cumbersome task.

4.2 Experiences as a Developer

From a developer perspective, the **interfaces** offered by APIs are sufficient, but not well documented. In addition, all projects faced restrictions in using third-party libraries, due to EMF binding.

Scalability was not a problem: the size of the models had no impact on functionality. However, the interoperability with the model repository was affected in terms of performance and latency (*cf.* Section 4.4). The lazy loading increased the performance for working on small parts of the models. However, when working on the whole model, lazy

loading had a negative impact on performance and could not be used in wide-area networks due to high latency.

Similar, the **transaction** support offered by CDO eases the realisation of consistency. Yet, the type of DBMS used as back-end actually impacts the semantics of transactions and the behaviour of the server. This requires to adapt the client code to the configuration of the server. Apart from that, the optimistic **versioning** of CDO requires large portion of error handling code in the client application due to exceptions thrown when concurrent updates had occurred.

The **validation** of the models enhanced the stability of the overall system. Yet, it also requires the developer to deal with possible constraint violations in the code, bloating the application. Finally, an update of the metamodel requires the re-write and adaptation of all client applications as the concept of data transfer objects [15] is lacking and models are directly exposed to clients.

While none of the projects utilises the history and the branching feature offered by CDO, they made use of the **notification** mechanism. Due to some weaknesses we faced when dealing with the propagation of changes and outdated documentation, we switched to a polling approach. While polling is normally considered suboptimal, it helped us to improve the stability of the code and hence, of the overall system.

4.3 Experiences as an Operator

Operating the CDO Server was generally experienced as a cumbersome and error-prone task also due to the marginal documentation and only few available configuration guides. In all projects we had to manually build the CDO Server in order to ensure persistence and security mechanisms are in place. This requires in-depth knowledge of OSGI and Eclipse and to some extent limits the automation of the server administration, *e.g.*, using DevOps tools. Administrative tools for the operator are limited to the basic Eclipse UI that offers basic access to the currently stored models. A shell or scripting interface is not available. The only administrator support is a configuration file that, however, only exposes a subset of the necessary configuration options.

In our work, we could not find a different way to change the database store except by re-building the CDO Server. Similarly, for us, the only way to realise **access** control, was to have the operator build a custom version including the *Security Manager*¹². Only once this feature has been enabled, the operator can manage the permissions of users, roles and operations through the Eclipse UI.

The **durability** of a set-up just like consistency is heavily dependent on the DBMS back-end. Crashes of CDO Server and connected clients occur when developers use features not provided by the current configuration such as transactions. In those cases, restarting the server as a means of recovery often not work and likely leads to complete data loss. All data is also lost when new metamodels are installed, as this requires to wipe the storage and rebuild the structure of the database.

Regarding **scalability**, the CDO Server in our usage scenarios has to be considered as a bottleneck when many probes and actuators are installed and/or a high access frequency is used. The operators in the projects suffer from the lack of built-in tools to analyse the performance and configuration guidelines. In all cases, the operators had to dig into code to identify performance bottlenecks and possible optimisations. While vertical scaling is physically limited, horizontal scaling is conceptually possible when using a scalable database such as MongoDB. Also, horizontal scaling on CDO level, *i.e.*, using multiple CDO Servers is an option. Experimenting with both approaches is subject to ongoing evaluations. Yet, in both cases we are challenged by sparse documentation.

4.4 Performance Experiences

While working with CDO, we experienced a satisfying performance during development and testing phases, but struggle in production set-ups. Mainly for large-scale and long running applications the performance behaviour of CDO is hard to predict any yields surprising results. This

¹² <https://www.uni-ulm.de/in/omi/blog/details/article/25032015brsetting-up-a-secure-cdo-server.html>

Server	
hardware	Virtual Machine with 4 cores, 8 GB RAM on AMD Opteron 2.6GHz
operating system	Ubuntu 14.04.2 LTS 64 bit, Linux 3.13.0-59-generic
Java virtual machine	OpenJDK 1.7.0_70
Eclipse version	Mars 4.5.2
CDO set-up	CDO 4.4, DB Store, access control enabled
MySQL version	Version 14.14, Distribution 5.5.44
Client	
hardware	Intel Core i5 1.9GHz 4 cores, 12 GB RAM
operating system	Arch Linux 64 bit, Linux 4.5.4-1-ARCH
Java virtual machine	OpenJDK 1.8.0_92
Eclipse version	Mars 4.5.1
CDO version	CDO 4.4

Table 3. Configuration of environment

section aims to illustrate some of these results through set of experiments.

4.4.1 Experiment Set-up and Methodology

The environment consists of a server and a client deployed on two hosts (*cf.* Table 3). Both hosts reside in the same local area network with a maximum bandwidth of 1 Gb/s. MySQL¹³ is used as database server. CDO server and database back-end are deployed on the same host implemented as virtual machine in an OpenStack cloud environment. CDO uses the DB store and hence the JDBC driver to connect to the database of TCP. The CDO server was built with security features and access control enabled.

All the experiments are run from a single client machine with only a single thread, hence there is no concurrent access to the CDO server. The connection to the server was opened once at the beginning of each experiment and then re-used throughout the experiment. This allows CDO to enable caching on client-side. Hence, all the results presented in the following serve as a lower bound for performance. The following results are derived from three independent runs and hence show an average value with deviations.

The use of CDO in models@run-time scenarios means that the system uses both read and write operations with read operations dominating. Nevertheless, for all three projects we also experience a constant load on write operations leading to growing models. This is mainly caused by the fact that (parts of) monitoring information is stored directly in CDO models.

¹³ <https://www.mysql.com/>

4.4.2 Write Performance

To validate the behaviour with an increasing amount of elements, the *write experiment* repeatedly opens a transaction, adds 100 new elements, and commits the transaction. This sequence is repeated 100 times so that at the end of the experiment 10,000 new elements were written to the CDO server. Between two transactions, the thread waits several seconds to enable an interleaving read experiment.

Figure 3. Write performance experience for 100 written elements with an overall increasing amount of elements stored in CDO

Figure 3 shows the results of this experiment. It contains the time required for opening a transaction (purple line) and for committing the 100 new elements (green line). While the time for opening a transaction is $O(1)$, the time required for committing new elements depends heavily on n , the number of elements already stored in the server. In particular, it grows with $O(n)$. In the worst case, it takes almost seven seconds to add 100 new elements.

4.4.3 Read Performance With Growing Model Size

The *first read experiment* elaborates the behaviour of reading from the CDO server while the server stores an increasing number of elements. The experiment interleaves with the *write experiment* as follows: whenever the write experiment sleeps after creating new elements, the *first read experiment* reads 100 randomly chosen elements from the server in a view (*i.e.*, read-only transaction).

Figure 4 shows the results of the experiment. The diagram shows that the time needed for reading 100 elements is widely independent from the number elements stored and after a warm-up phase drops to a constant value.

4.4.4 Read Performance With Growing Read Size

The *second read experiment* elaborates the behaviour of reading a growing number of elements from a CDO server storing 10,000 elements. In the first iteration, 100 elements are read. Then 99 further iterations follow and in each iteration, the 100 more elements are read. Hence, the last iteration reads the entire server state.

Figure 5 shows the results of the experiment. Not surprisingly, the time consumed for reading a linearly increasing

Figure 4. Read performance experience for 100 read elements with an overall increasing amount of elements stored in CDO

Figure 5. Read performance experience for increasing amount of elements read and fixed amount of elements stored in CDO

number of elements from the CDO server increases linearly. Hence, on average the time needed for reading an individual element stays constant.

4.4.5 Resource Utilisation in Experiment Set-up

While running the three experiments, the server and client are continuously monitored. The monitored metrics for the CDO related processes are CPU utilisation, memory consumption, and the used network bandwidth, separately for the client and the server side. Analysing the monitoring data, in all experiments the CPU and memory utilisation on both client and server side is reasonable: the load is rather stable, and never exceeds a note worthy threshold. Yet, while executing the write performance experiment, the network utilisation on the server side shows a similarity to the time required for committing new elements to the CDO server.

Figure 6 represents the network utilisation for one write performance experiment. On client side, the network bandwidth is stable over time (green line), although the amount of total elements in the CDO server increased. On the server side, the network bandwidth increased linearly with the amount of total elements stored (purple line). To conclude this behaviour, the CDO server probably writes to the

Figure 6. Network bandwidth for a write performance experiment on client and server side

MySQL database via TCP synchronously, which causes the network bandwidth utilisation and the increasing time on client side for the write performance experiment.

4.4.6 Summary

The experiments show that the read performance experienced widely only depends on the number of elements read. The write performance for adding new elements, however, grows with the size of the model which is limiting. Although CDO offers several configuration parameters for performance tweaking¹⁴, none of the settings notably influenced the write performance. The utilisation metrics showed a clear relation with the network bandwidth on server side. Improving the performance of the CDO server in write heavy use cases is subject to ongoing investigations.

5. Discussion

This section discusses the consequences of the experiences described in Section 4. It starts with a concluding summary, then presents the lessons learnt, and finally presents a wish list of desired features in CDO that eases the life of particularly operators and developers.

5.1 Experience Summary

Our experiences show that CDO is a tool that has been developed for MDE. In short, it is better suited for use, the more abstract a user's role and the less automation is needed. A DSL designer, as the creator of metamodels and constraints, sees a rich tool in CDO and its Eclipse integration for design-time support. The creation, validation, and versioning of models and the respective metamodels is well supported by the Eclipse IDE. Based on the extensibility of the Eclipse IDE also more specific tools can be integrated, *e.g.*, the OCL or Xtext tool.

For developers, CDO offers basic features that fully supports implementing actuators and probes in a models@runtime environment. Yet, the programming model requires getting used to. Even experienced (Java) programmers have

to adapt their programming style to constraints imposed by CDO. For instance, the way CDO treats equality and identity of objects is contrary to how the Java collections framework deals with these aspects. According to our experience, the sparse and often outdated documentation does not sufficiently guide inexperienced CDO developers. From an architectural point of view, data transfer objects are missing. This lack of abstraction layer leads to a tight coupling between CDO-specific and actual application code in client applications. The fact that CDO-specific code in client applications depends directly on the setup of the CDO Server is sub-optimal from a management point of view, as applying changes to the server configuration may influence the client application.

In our experience, from all the three roles, operators are least pleased with CDO. This is probably due to the fact that they are furthest away from DSL designer. Also, operators are not directly foreseen in the MDE paradigm. While CDO offers mandatory features such as access control and support for different databases, the setup, monitoring, and operation of a CDO Server is a widely manual task that is error-prone and time consuming; often complicated by the sparse documentation. Operators in our projects are missing administrative tools and find performance issues hard to resolve.

5.2 Lessons Learnt

Not all negative experience made in the projects stem from the technical domain: Operators suffer from the behaviour of DSL designer and developers. Here, we experienced that the workarounds these two groups introduce to cope with shortcomings and to realise advanced features, fall on the operators' feet.

This is due to that fact that many of the workarounds lead to a frequent update of the metamodels or require a re-occurring reconfiguration of the database. The easy access to metamodels and their high abstraction level, tempts particularly DSL designers to do quick updates to the metamodel. In consequence, this imposes a load on the developers that have to adapt their code to the new models and particularly on the operators that not only have to reconfigure the CDO Server, but also to re-deploy all probes and actuators to support the new metamodels. Here, an automatised deployment helps a lot. Yet, this is complicated by the way CDO is build and operates (*cf.* Section 4.3).

Due to organisational shortcomings with frequently updated models, CACTOS and CloudSocket suffer from data loss on a regular basis. PaaSage, in contrast, has established a rigid release cycle of both metamodels and code dependent on the metamodels that avoids this trap.

The experiments show that the read performance experienced widely only depends on the number of elements read. The write performance for adding new elements, however, grows with the size of the model. This fact requires specific counter measures to be taken by the system architect. First, CDO views should be used instead of transactions

¹⁴https://wiki.eclipse.org/CDO/Tweaking_Performance

whenever possible. Second, each client in the should should have a performance configurations¹⁵ that takes into account this client's way of access and frequency frequency to the repository. Third, models should whenever possible be designed such that they have a fixed size and changes are realised by updating existing elements instead of creating new elements. As before, the realisation of all of the steps require rigidity from a management and quality assurance point of view.

5.3 Desired Features

For the future, we expect more advanced features for both CDO and EMF that truly enable its use in production.

Crucial to this and a more wide-spread uptake of the technology is a better and particularly more up-to-date documentation. This helps developers using the correct and up-to-date APIs, and operators to pick the right database and right configuration for their particular use case. Operators (and system administrators) also benefit from more support tailored to their user group. Here, the provisioning of sophisticated UIs plays a major role: They can help with installing, updating, and managing (new) metamodels; they can support the configuration and entire set-up of CDO server; they help with changing database backends or scaling out the CDO deployment. Finally, they support the monitoring of the CDO, the hardware, and the system usage and provide suggestions on how to improve the configuration. The provisioning of pre-built binaries helps the integration of CDO server and client bundles in automated build chains and ease the deployment and update not only of the server, but of the entire system.

The support of a run-time update mechanism for metamodels [11] absolutely necessary when the evolution of metamodels over time shall be supported. Solving this problem would also give EMF/CDO and consequently MDE a competitive advantage over the use of mere database mechanisms (*e.g.*, tables) or object-relational mappers that both suffer from the same problem, but have not been able to solve them satisfactory.

For developers, a more generic abstraction layer eases integrating CDO with other parts of the system. In particular, the provisioning of a layer with DTO (data transfer objects) functionality can decouple release cycles of metamodels and client code. Finally, a more automatised synchronisation of OCL constraints will be helpful for the developer and widens the adoption of the technology stack.

6. Related Work

Other authors approve our view that CDO is well-suited as a model repository from a DSL designer's perspective due to its support for persistence, collaborative work, versioning [8]. Yet, due to the lacking support of scalable models it is proposed to shift the scaling responsibility to the DSL de-

signer. Other authors identify that using relational DBMS as storage back-ends limits the performance and scalability of CDO [2]. A discussion and comparison of new storage solutions concludes that NoSQL based repositories overcome these limitations [2].

A roadmap towards scalability in MDE is presented in [9]. The authors suggest further research in: model query languages, scalable model repositories and model transformations. CDO as the state is highlighted for supporting collaboration based on transactions and views, but the lack of mature support for conflict management and merging is noted. As alternative Morsa is pointed out with the focus on scalable persistence but without access control, version management or security [6].

The Morsa approach [6] targets the scalability of the model repository. CDO is referred to as the most mature model repository for EMF. Yet the scalability of CDO is criticised, especially for large models (> 600 MB). Hence a new model repository is introduced focusing performance and scalability instead of consistency. Based on the EMF resource API and MongoDB as storage back-end, Morsa promises better scalability than CDO. Yet [6] does not evaluate CDO with MongoDB against their approach.

Neo4EMF [3] is a similar approach to improve scalability. Instead of using MongoDB, they propose the graph based Neo4j database. CDO is referred as the de facto standard model repository for EMF based on its features, however indicating operator related requirements such as monitoring or horizontal scalability are missing.

EMF in combination with CDO has been examined in various scenarios including models@run-time. CDO for models@run-time is discussed by [7]. Requirements for models@run-time are outlined and correlated to CDO and further model repositories. The authors conclude that CDO only fits partially the needs of models@run-time, but that there is currently no available solution fitting all requirements. Therefore, they propose the Kevoree Modeling Framework, which provides a toolset to model, structure, and reason about data at design- and run-time, while introducing as little overhead as possible. CDO in the cloud context is considered by [11] with the focus on migrating models. In this context, the lacking model migration support of CDO is further elaborated leading to a solution proposal.

7. Conclusions and Future Work

In this paper, we reported on more than three years of experience with realising and operating models@run-time in cloud scenarios using a technology stack consisting of EMF and CDO. First, we identified three main roles in models@run-time, assigned them specific tasks in the life-cycle of models@run-time, and derived requirements for tools to support models@run-time. Next, we introduced the technological stack of EMF and CDO. We can state that CDO basically supports the models@run-time paradigm.

¹⁵https://wiki.eclipse.org/CDO/Tweaking_Performance

Yet, CDO does not support all three roles to the same extent and shows performance limitations. CDO is well-suited for DSL designers and we only experienced minor divergences with our requirements. In contrast, the use of CDO may be cumbersome for developers for operators. For both roles we experienced a steep learning curve and several lacking features that hindered the implementation of models@run-time in scalable cloud scenarios. Based on our experiences, we derive a wish list to the EMF/CDO developers on how to extend the tools.

Concluding, we do not discourage the use of EMF/CDO for our scenario, but we recommend that its adoption for similar use cases is carefully evaluated and that general best practices in software engineering are adopted. In particular, changes to metamodels and their impact on the models@run-time environment require the establishment of strict project management and rigid release and update cycles.

Future work will focus on a quantitative evaluation of the experiences in particular with respect to an extended performance evaluation. Based on artificial and actual load, we will produce a performance model that helps identifying bottlenecks and scaling options beyond the performance experiments presented in 4.4. Ideally, the results of the extended performance evaluation will lead to an operator guide for CDO server for productively used and large scale set ups.

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